

The Effects of Rare Resources and Organizational Culture on Firm Performance through Competitive Advantage: Study of Small Construction Consultant Services Companies Member of INKINDO Association of Central Sulawesi

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Abstract

Infrastructure development is access to all activities used to fulfill the community service system, including government activities, social activities, economy and industry in order to facilitate the flow of distribution of goods and services. Companies in the field of construction consulting services have an important role in the development of this infrastructure, especially in the areas of planning and supervision. This research analyzes the relationship between rare resources and organizational culture on firm performance through competitive advantage. Using a non-probability method for sampling, with a census sampling design type. Researchers used a questionnaire as a data collection method, which was then analyzed using the PLS-based SEM method. Based on data from 61 small qualified construction consulting companies in the INKINDO Association of Central Sulawesi, research findings show that Rare Resources, Organizational Culture, and Competitive Advantage partially influence Firm Performance. Competitive Advantage can act as a mediator in the influence of Rare Resources and Organizational Culture on Firm Performance.

1. Introduction

The success of a country's economic development is reflected in its economic growth. Every country in the world has the main goal of economic activity, namely stable and rapid economic growth, including Indonesia. Economic growth and equitable development throughout Indonesia are

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the underlying reasons for moving the National Capital (Kementerian PPN/Bappenas, 2021). The President and DPR have enacted the Law on National Capital in Law No. 3 of 2022, which was ratified on February 15, 2022, under the name Nusantara (Republic of Indonesia, 2022).

The initial stage in the development of the National Capital City is the development of infrastructure, institutions, and the transfer of Civil Apparatus (ASN). This development certainly requires a supporting role from the areas around the location of the National Capital in meeting needs, raw materials, labor resources, and other needs required by the National Capital. Several regional governments that have signed a commitment are willing to become buffer zones for the National Capital, namely East Kalimantan, North Kalimantan, South Kalimantan, Central Sulawesi, West Sulawesi, and South Sulawesi (Fauzan, 2022). Geographically, the province of Central Sulawesi is closest to the province of East Kalimantan compared to the provinces of West Sulawesi and South Sulawesi.

Figure 1. Image Capture of Distance between East Kalimantan Province and Central Sulawesi Province (Google Maps, 2023)

Based on Figure 1 above, you can see the position of Central Sulawesi Province which is directly opposite East Kalimantan Province. This provides advantages for the province of Central Sulawesi in distributing its resources via sea routes. The Central Sulawesi Provincial Government has prepared a food area for residents of the National Capital, as stated in the Governor's Decree No.: 504/117.1/DBMPR-G.ST/2022 concerning the determination of food areas, as well as recommendations for the Archipelago Food Area by BAPPEDA as stated in Decision No. 504/71/Bappeda (Fauzan, 2022).

Infrastructure development cannot be separated from construction activities. Construction is a development activity, while construction activities are in the form of construction, maintenance and repair. Based on Law No. 18 of 1999 which regulates construction services, there are 3 (three) types of construction services, namely construction planners (consultant planners), construction implementers (contractors), and construction supervisors (supervisory consultants) (Republic of Indonesia, 1999). Construction consulting service companies work under the auspices of associations/organizations that oversee their performance, one of which is the INKINDO Association. One of the first consultant associations in Indonesia was established on June 20, 1979, and its members are spread across 34 provinces throughout Indonesia (INKINDO, 2023).

Table 1
Construction Consultant Companies Joined in INKINDO Central Sulawesi 2019-2022

No.	Qualification	Year			
		2019	2020	2021	2022

1	Small	67	73	85	69
2	Middle	5	5	5	5
3	Big	0	0	0	0

Source: *INKINDO Sulawesi Tengah, 2023*

Based on data collected by INKINDO Central Sulawesi, construction consulting services companies under the auspices of INKINDO experienced ups and downs in firm growth from 2019 to 2022. The decline in the number of construction consulting services companies due to various factors which have resulted in companies having to go out of business has become a challenge in itself for companies that are still surviving and companies in other fields in the same industry. This is because construction consulting service companies are interrelated with other companies, such as construction equipment providers, construction material providers, etc.

The decrease in the number of companies indicates a decline in firm performance. The performance of a firm can be influenced by various factors, namely external and internal factors of the firm. External factors are factors that cannot be controlled by the firm because they come from outside the firm, while internal factors are factors that can be controlled by the firm itself. Therefore, it is important for companies to analyze internal factors to identify the firm's weaknesses and strengths, so that the firm can predict opportunities and anticipate the threats it will face. One internal factor is firm resources, especially rare resources. Companies that have rare resources enable these companies to create optimal performance (Pearce II & Robinson Jr, 2013). This is supported by empirical evidence in previous research which shows the influence of rare resources on performance (Baia et al., 2019; Purwanti et al., 2017), however on the other hand there is still research which finds show that rare resources have no effect on performance (Ferreira & Fernandes, 2017; Moscare-Balanquit, 2021; Semaan et al., 2020).

Apart from qualified resources as a determining factor in improving firm performance, companies also need to have an organizational culture that works well in order to achieve firm goals. Organizational culture has an influence on firm performance variables in the long term, organizational culture is an important factor in determining the success or failure of a firm in the next decade (Tika, 2010). This is supported by empirical evidence in previous research shows that organizational culture influences performance (Dyahrini et al., 2020; Ghalem et al., 2018; Hoiron et al., 2018; Kaidu, 2019; Kimata & Itakura, 2021; Nuryanto et al., 2020), however on the other hand there is still research which finds show that organizational culture has no effect on performance (Muliati et al., 2020; Sinha & Dhall, 2018).

In facing industrial competition, it is necessary to have a competitive strategy. The role of competitive strategy for companies is to achieve competitive advantage over internal strengths and weaknesses as well as external opportunities and threats that can influence firm performance (Abonda & Machuki, 2018). Competitive advantage is included as a mediating variable on the influence of rare resources and organizational culture on firm performance by considering that there is a need for competitiveness between companies in order to improve performance and maintain the firm amidst intense competition with similar companies. With competitiveness between similar companies, companies will pay attention to rare resources (Baia et al., 2019; Moscare-Balanquit, 2021; Purwanti et al., 2017) and organizational culture (Dyahrini et al., 2020; Nuryanto et al., 2020), so that the firm is able to maintain its performance.

Referring to studies from several previous studies that there are research gaps, it is necessary to conduct further studies regarding the influence of scarce resources and organizational culture on firm performance through competitive advantage using the research object of small qualified construction consulting services companies in Central Sulawesi.

2. Materials and Methods

This research uses a non-probability method for sampling, with a census sampling design type, namely a sampling technique where all members of the population are sampled (Sugiyono, 2017). The selection of respondents in this study was based on the following criteria: (a) Companies that have been actively joining the INKINDO Association for at least 3 years; (b) The respondent has the highest structural position, namely Commissioner, Director or Manager and (c) The lowest possible education is Bachelor (S1). The analytical method used in this research is Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) based on PLS (Partial Least Square) with the help of SmartPLS 4 software. PLS is designed to complete multiple regression when specific problems occur in the data, such as small research sample sizes, missing data and multicollinearity (Ghozali & Kusumadewi, 2023). Although PLS is used to determine whether there is a relationship between variables, it can also be used to confirm theories. SEM-PLS does not require a large number of samples, the minimum recommended is between 30 until 100 samples (Ghozali & Kusumadewi, 2023).

The variables in this study use indicators as measuring tools adopted from several previous studies. The Rare Resources variable in this study was measured using 4 indicators referring to the research of (Baia et al., 2019; Moscare-Balanquit, 2021; Purwanti et al., 2017). The Organizational Culture variable is measured using 2 indicators based on Schein's theory, which refers to the research of (Ghalem et al., 2018; Kimata & Itakura, 2021). The Competitive Advantage variable is measured using 3 indicators (Abonda & Machuki, 2018; Semaan et al., 2020). Firm Performance Variables are measured using 4 indicators based on the opinion of Kaplan & Norton, where the Balanced Scorecard can be used to measure firm performance, because it can measure the overall business perspective (Kaplan & Norton, 2015), which refers to previous research which has proven that these indicators can measure firm performance (Abonda & Machuki, 2018; Sawlani et al., 2022).

This research focuses on analyzing the relationship between rare resources, organizational culture, competitive advantage, and firm performance in construction consulting services companies, with a focus on companies with small qualifications. The variables of this research consist of independent variables, namely rare resources and organizational culture, while the dependent variable is firm performance, as well as a mediating variable, namely competitive advantage.

Source: Developed for thesis study, 2023

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Based on this conceptual framework, the hypotheses in this research are:

- H1: Rare resources influence firm performance.
- H2: Organizational culture influences firm performance.
- H3: Rare resources influence competitive advantage.

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H4: Organizational culture influences competitive advantage.

H5: Competitive advantage influences firm performance.

H6: Rare resources influence firm performance through competitive advantage.

H7: Organizational culture influences firm performance through competitive advantage.

3. Results and Discussions

In this study, researchers distributed 69 questionnaires, but 68 questionnaires were returned. Based on previously determined respondent criteria, only 61 questionnaires met the requirements for research. Based on the results of data processing on 61 respondents, information was obtained that there were 53 respondents (86.89%) male and 8 respondents (13.11%) female. This shows that the majority of those in charge/holders of the highest structural positions in small qualified construction consulting companies in the INKINDO Association of Central Sulawesi are male. The next category is based on the age of the respondent, there are 15 respondents (24.59%) with an age range of 21-30 years, 19 respondents (31.15%) with an age range of 31-40 years, 20 respondents (32.79%) with a range of aged 41-50 years, 6 respondents (9.84%) with an age range of 51-60 years, and 1 respondent (1.64%) with an age range of >60 years. Based on the Dependency Burden Figure (ABK) indicator according to the Indonesian Ministry of Health, the majority of respondents in this study fell into the productive age group (15-64 years old) (Kemenkes RI, 2022). It can be interpreted that the highest structural leader of a small qualified construction consulting services firm in the INKINDO Association of Central Sulawesi can carry out activities effectively and efficiently.

The next category is based on the respondent's education level, there are 55 respondents (90.16%) with a Bachelor's (S1) education level, and 6 respondents (9.84%) with a Master's (S2) education level. This shows that small qualified construction consulting companies in the INKINDO Association of Central Sulawesi have the potential to be able to maintain competition and improve their performance. Based on the category of the position held by the respondent, all respondents, or 61 respondents (100%) in this study have the position of director. This shows that the respondents of this study best understand the firm's conditions. The next category is based on firm age, there are 10 companies (16.39%) with a firm age range of 3-5 years, 19 companies (31.15%) with a firm age range of 6-10 years, 26 companies (42.62 %) with a firm age range of 11-20 years, 3 companies (4.92%) with a firm age range of 21-30 years, and 3 companies (4.92%) with a firm age range of >30 years, this shows that the firm has the high experience, so it is assumed that it has succeeded in improving its performance and can survive amidst competition.

Partial Least Square (PLS) Analysis

The SEM method based on Partial Least Square (PLS) is used as a data processing technique in this research. Researchers used PLS software, namely SmartPLS version 4.0, which was developed by the SmartPLS GmbH firm located in Oststeinbek, Germany. PLS is a strong analysis method because it eliminates the assumptions of OLS (Ordinary Least Square) regression, such as data must be normally distributed in a multivariate manner and there is no multicollinearity between independent variables (Ghozali & Kusumadewi, 2023). The PLS method consists of two basic stages, namely validating the measurement model (outer model) to see how each indicator can present its variables and testing the structural model (inner model) to see the relationship between variables.

Model Evaluation (Outer Model and Inner Model)

Apart from the tests above, researchers also tested the estimation of path coefficients which identify the strength of the relationship between latent variables, both directly and indirectly. This test was carried out using the bootstrapping method using SmartPLS software version 4.0.

Source: Primary Data Processing Results with SmartPLS, 2023

Figure 2. Measurement Model (Outer Loading)

Information:

- RR: Rare Resources
- CA: Competitive Advantage
- OC: Organizational Culture
- P : Performance

There are three assessments of the measurement model (outer model) in the data analysis technique with SmartPLS, namely the validity test and the reliability test. The validity test consists of convergent validity and discriminant validity, while the reliability test consists of composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha. Convergent validity (validity test) is carried out to measure whether a questionnaire is valid or not (Sekaran & Bougie, 2017). Based on Figure 3 above, it can be concluded that the items from the indicators for each variable rare resources (X1), organizational culture (X2), competitive advantage (M), and firm performance (Y) have met the requirements for convergent validity, because they have a value loading factor >0.7.

Table 2
Discriminant Validity Test Results

Variable	\sqrt{AVE}	Correlation Score Between Latent Variables			
		Rare Resources	Organizational culture	Competitive Advantage	Firm performance
Rare Resources	0.771		0.183	0.486	0.485
Organizational culture	0.787	0.183		0.624	0.558
Competitive Advantage	0.801	0.486	0.624		0.688
Firm performance	0.785	0.485	0.558	0.688	

Source: Primary Data Processing Results with SmartPLS, 2023

Discriminant validity is used to compare loading values to find out whether the construct has adequate discriminant, where the value of the targeted construct must be greater than the value of other constructs (Ghozali & Kusumadewi, 2023). Based on Table 2 above, it can be concluded that the indicators for the variables rare resources, organizational culture, competitive advantage

and firm performance have met the requirements for discriminant validity. This is based on Fornell-Larcker Criterion calculations, it is found that the value between variables is still below the \sqrt{AVE} value, thus all indicators for each variable in this study have met discriminant validity.

Table 3
Composite Reliability Results

Variabel	Composite Reliability	Cronbach's Alpha	Description
Rare Resources	0.935	0.920	Reliabel
Organizational culture	0.929	0.912	Reliabel
Competitive Advantage	0.951	0.944	Reliabel
Firm performance	0.953	0.948	Reliabel

Source: Primary Data Processing Results with SmartPLS, 2023

Composite reliability is considered better in estimating the internal consistency of a construct because it is able to measure the true value of the reliability of a construct (Ghozali & Kusumadewi, 2023). Based on the composite reliability results in Table 3 above, the instrument in this study meets the reliability requirements, because it has a composite reliability value of >0.7. So it can be concluded that the construct has good reliability. Structural model testing (inner model) to see the relationship between the significance value of R-square (R2) of the model used. The structural model in PLS is tested by measuring the R2 value and path coefficient through comparing the t-statistics with the t-table in the SmartPLS output.

Source: Primary Data Processing Results with SmartPLS, 2023
Figure 3. Structural Model (Inner Model)

Table 4; R-Square Value

Variabel	R Square
Competitive Advantage	0.533
Firm performance	0.542

Source: Primary Data Processing Results with SmartPLS, 2023

Table 4 shows the Competitive Advantage (M) variable which is influenced by Rare Resources (X1) and Organizational Culture (X2), with an R-square value of 0.533. The R-square value shows that 53.3% of the Competitive Advantage variable can be influenced by the Rare Resources variable (X1) and the Organizational Culture variable (X2), while the remaining 46.7% is influenced by other variables outside the variables studied. Meanwhile, for the Firm Performance variable (Y), which is influenced by the Rare Resources variable (X1), the Organizational Culture variable (X2), and the Competitive Advantage variable (M), an R-square value of 0.542 was obtained. The R-square value shows that 54.2% of the Firm Performance variable (Y) is influenced by the Rare Resources variable (X1), Organizational Culture variable (X2), and Competitive Advantage variable (M), while the remaining 45.8% is influenced by other variables. outside the variables studied.

Hypothesis Test

Table 5
Hypothesis Test Results

Variable	Original Samples (O)	t-statistic	P value	Description
RR→P	0.237	2.803	0.005	Significant
OC→P	0.257	2.034	0.042	Significant
RR→CA	0.385	4.188	0.000	Significant
OC→CA	0.553	5.418	0.000	Significant
CA→P	0.413	3.392	0.001	Significant
RR→CA→P	0.159	2.473	0.013	Significant
OC→CA→P	0.229	2.894	0.004	Significant

Source: Primary Data Processing Results with SmartPLS, 2023

Based on the results of the hypothesis test in Table 5 above, it is known that rare resources have a positive and significant effect on firm performance, where the analysis results show the t-statistic value (2.803) > t-table value (1.96) and are significant at 5%, Thus H1 is accepted. Meanwhile, the organizational culture variable has no positive effect and is not significant, where the analysis results show the t-statistic value (2.034) > t-table value (1.96) and is not significant at 5%, thus H2 is accepted.

Furthermore, the results of the analysis on the variables rare resources and organizational culture are known to have a positive and significant influence on competitive advantage, where the results of the analysis show the t-statistic value (4.188) > t-table value (1.96) and are significant at 5%, thus H3 is accepted. Meanwhile, the results of the analysis of the organizational culture variable on competitive advantage obtained a t-statistic value (5.418) > t-table value (1.96) and were significant at 5%, thus H4 was accepted.

The results of the analysis of the competitive advantage variable on firm performance show the t-statistic value (3.392) > t-table value (1.96) and is significant at 5%, thus H5 is accepted. Meanwhile, the results of the analysis on the indirect influence of rare resources on firm performance through competitive advantage showed that the t-statistic value (2.473) > t-table value (1.96) was significant at 5%, thus H6 was accepted. The results of the mediation test on the indirect influence of organizational culture on firm performance through competitive advantage obtained a t-statistic value (2.894) > t-table value (1.96) and were significant at 5%, thus H7 was accepted.

Discussion

The Influence of Rare Resources Variables on Firm Performance

The results of the analysis show that rare resources have a positive and significant effect on firm performance. This indicates that rare resources can improve the performance of small qualified construction consulting companies that are members of the INKINDO Association of Central Sulawesi. Thus, the greater the scarce resources a firm has, the better the firm's performance will increase. This finding is in line with the theory that scarce resources are resources that can increase firm profits so that companies achieve optimal performance (Hitt et al., 2007; Pearce II & Robinson Jr, 2013). The results of this research are also in line with the results of previous research which stated that scarce resources have an influence in improving firm performance (Baia et al., 2019; Purwanti et al., 2017).

The Influence of Organizational Culture Variables on Firm Performance

The results of the analysis show that organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on firm performance. This indicates that organizational culture can improve performance in small qualified construction consulting companies that are members of the INKINDO Association of Central Sulawesi. Thus, the better the organizational culture a firm has, the more firm performance will increase. This finding is in line with the theory that organizational culture is an important factor in determining the success and failure of a firm in the long term, so that the better the organizational culture, the better the firm's performance (Moeljono, 2003; Tika, 2010). The results of this research are also in line with the results of previous research which shows that the better the organizational culture a company has, the better the company's performance will be (Dyahrini et al., 2020; Ghalem et al., 2018; Hoiron et al., 2018; Kaidu, 2019; Kimata & Itakura, 2021; Nuryanto et al., 2020).

The Influence of Rare Resources Variables on Competitive Advantage

The results of the analysis show that rare resources have a positive and significant effect on competitive advantage. This indicates that rare resources can increase the competitive advantage of small qualified construction consulting companies that are members of the INKINDO Association of Central Sulawesi. Thus, the greater the rare resources owned by the firm, the more influence the firm will increase in competition. This finding is in line with the theory that resources that are rarely found in competing companies, the more these resources are needed by customers and will ultimately become a source of competitive advantage for the firm (Barney & Clark, 2007; Pearce II & Robinson Jr, 2013). The results of this research are also in line with the results of previous research which states that the scarcer a firm's resources are, the more superior the firm is to other companies (Baia et al., 2019; Moscare-Balanquit, 2021; Purwanti et al., 2017).

The Influence of Organizational Culture Variables on Competitive Advantage

The results of the analysis show that organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on competitive advantage. This indicates that organizational culture can increase competitive advantage in small qualified construction consulting companies that are members of the INKINDO Association of Central Sulawesi. Thus, the better the organizational culture a firm has, the more it will influence the firm's competitiveness. This finding is in line with the theory that organizational culture is believed to be the main determining factor in the success of an organization by implementing aspects or values of organizational culture so that the organization is able to provide a positive image for its development (Mangkunegara, 2017). The results of this research are also in line with the results of previous research which stated that competitiveness cannot be considered without organizational culture, because almost all business development has gone through high organizational culture (Azeem et al., 2021; Azhad et al., 2018).

The Influence of Competitive Advantage Variables on Firm Performance

The results of the analysis show that competitive advantage has a positive and significant effect on firm performance. This indicates that competitive advantage can improve firm performance in small qualified construction consulting companies that are members of the INKINDO Association of Central Sulawesi. Thus, competitiveness will improve firm performance. This finding is in line with the theory that increasing a superior competitive position can trigger a firm to improve its performance in order to win the competition against similar companies in its environment (Assauri, 2016; Porter, 2008). The results of this research are also in line with the results of previous research which shows that the existence of competitive advantages can encourage companies to improve their performance so that they are able to face competition with their competitors (Abonda & Machuki, 2018; Baia et al., 2019; Dyahrini et al., 2020; Hoiron et al., 2018; Moscare-Balanquit, 2021; Nuryanto et al., 2020; Purwanti et al., 2017; Sawlani et al., 2022; Semaan et al., 2020).

The Influence of Rare Resources Variables on Firm Performance Through Competitive Advantage

The results of the analysis show that rare resources have a positive and significant effect on firm performance through competitive advantage. This indicates that competitive advantage can provide a mediating role in the indirect relationship between rare resources and firm performance in small qualified construction consulting companies that are members of the INKINDO Association of Central Sulawesi. Thus, if scarce resources have the potential to become resources that can increase competition, then these resources will have an impact on increasing firm performance optimally.

This finding is in line with the theory that the greater the potential of a firm's rare resources as a source of competitive advantage, the greater the increase in firm performance (Hitt et al., 2007). The results of this research are also in line with the results of previous research which shows that competitive advantage will strengthen the role of scarce resources in improving company performance (Baia et al., 2019; Moscare-Balanquit, 2021; Purwanti et al., 2017).

The Influence of Organizational Culture Variables on Firm Performance Through Competitive Advantage

The results of the analysis show that organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on firm performance through competitive advantage. This indicates that competitive advantage can provide a mediating role in the indirect relationship between organizational culture and firm performance in small qualified construction consulting companies that are members of the INKINDO Association of Central Sulawesi. Thus, if there are more and more similar companies, then the firm is required to improve and develop its organizational culture, even though it is difficult to change, in order to improve its performance and survive from other similar companies. This finding is in line with the theory that organizational culture has a very strong role in the development of each individual in the firm to jointly carry out competitive strategies in facing competitors and improving firm performance (Schein, 2004; Tika, 2010). The results of this research are also in line with the results of previous research which shows that competitive advantage strengthens the influence of organizational culture on company performance (Dyahrini et al., 2020; Nuryanto et al., 2020).

4. Conclusion

Rare resources and organizational culture have an influence on firm performance, both directly and indirectly through competitive advantage. Human resources are a rare resource owned by the

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majority of small qualified construction consulting companies in the INKINDO Association, where one of the rare human resources is workers who have SKK (Work Skills Certificate). The more scarce the firm's human resources are, the easier it is for the firm to achieve a superior position and create optimal performance. Meanwhile, in the organizational culture of the majority of companies, they pay more attention to the values held by each individual firm. The self-identity inherent in each individual is also a reflection of the firm itself. Therefore, it is important for companies to continue to evaluate their organizational culture, so that they can outperform similar companies and improve their performance.

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